

THE MAIN FEATURES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF RAILWAYS IN UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

Currently, the modernization and renewal of our country, the formation of a qualitatively new, modern structural structure of our economy, and the comprehensive development of our regions are inextricably linked with the improvement of the transport and communication system.

The last two to three decades of the last century were characterized by the expansion of economic relations between the countries of the world and the globalization of the economy. This process is facilitated by the following factors:

First, world trade is becoming more open, more countries are benefiting from it, and trying to expand their participation in the world market, where everything needed for production needs can be bought. is doing The revival of trade increases the need for transport.

Secondly, production technologies are becoming more and more complex, first of all, special emphasis is being placed on the creation of airplanes, sea ships,

locomotives, large cargo vehicles, multi-seater buses, powerful computers, and telecommunications equipment. There is no way to implement these projects without the large involvement of international capital in the implementation of projects that require a lot of investment. During the construction of a large-scale enterprise, general transportation of construction materials and equipment is carried out between countries, and after its construction, raw materials, materials, complete parts and finished products are transported.

Thirdly, transcontinental rail transport routes connecting distant countries will be established to serve economic relations.

Fourth, the globalization of the economy has led to the expansion of production cooperation between countries located in different continents due to the pursuit of maximum profit. It is becoming common for an enterprise operating in every country to become a partner of a large foreign company, to supply it with

necessary supplies, spare parts and complete equipment.

Fifth, for the globalization of the economy, first of all, a developed means of transport capable of meeting the growing needs of the world economy is needed for the transportation of goods. However, in the conditions of increasing exchange of goods, it is becoming more and more difficult to control the quality, technical and environmental safety of the traded products. More and more cargoes cross the borders between countries, they have to go through customs control and, if necessary, undergo various inspections. It is becoming more and more difficult to control the prices of monopolistic producers, that is, both over the raised prices and over the cheap ones. That is why the world community is creating social institutions at various levels to manage and regulate world trade.

The processes of integration taking place in the world have a satisfactory effect on the activity of the global transport system, which is becoming a world railway network. According to this plan, "Uzbekistan Railways" is open to mutually beneficial cooperation with all interested parties.

The Republic of Uzbekistan strives to strengthen its political and economic independence, to actively enter the world community, to provide the national economy with high-level transport. For this, first of all, it is necessary to develop the railways, because the goal can be achieved only if the railways, which are the lifeblood of the country, are developed. Our country is geographically located in such a way that the main transit cargo transportation between Europe and Asia is carried out through our territories. Due to

these main reasons, the comprehensive work on the restoration and development of railway networks and the creation of the unified national transport network of Uzbekistan is aimed at these goals.

Steel highways are the main transport system of the country and an important strategic branch of the national economy of Uzbekistan. More cargo is transported on the railways than all other means of transport on the country's railways. Its importance is especially great when goods are imported and exported. In addition, the transit cargo flow connecting the North-South, East and West passes through the railways of Uzbekistan.

Compared to other types of transport, railways certainly have many advantages. They are as follows:

First of all, it is capable of carrying out transport work regardless of any weather conditions, its stability, that is, its ability to continue its work without stopping even during a hurricane, heavy rain or snow. Therefore, freight transportation processes on railways have never been suspended due to weather conditions;

Second, there is a system of recovery and fire prevention trains that are ready to arrive at the scene of an emergency accident at short notice after receiving the train dispatcher's order. Emergency recovery trains are equipped with technical means that allow to pull wagons from the place of disaster, repair and repair damaged tracks, electrical transmitter, signaling and communication lines in a short period of time;

Thirdly, the high transport capacity and mobilization ability of railway transport allows to transport people and equipment from the regions of natural disasters and man-made disasters.

After the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the government of the country began to attach great importance to the development of railway transport. On November 7, 1994, the state joint-stock company "Uzbekistan Railways" ("Uzbekskiy zheleznyy dorogi") was established at the base of the Central Asian Railways located on the territory of the republic. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 2, 2001 "On Measures to Equitize and Remove Monopoly of Railway Transport" and Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 108 dated March 3, 2001 "On the decision of Uzbekistan Railways "On improving the management organization of WAC" gave a new impetus to the ongoing reforms. In these documents, special importance is attached to the creation of market infrastructures and a competitive environment in the field of passenger and cargo transportation. The main tasks of the network are defined as follows:

First, to create a single railway transport network;

Secondly, to continue the electrification of the main sections of railways;

Thirdly, railways with the transfer of telecommunications to the fiber-optic system

development of railway transport infrastructures, including improvement;

Fourthly, the establishment of a private repair base of the active fleet;

Fifth, to increase the republic's export potential and search for an alternative transport corridor that provides access to the world market;

In the past, the Great Silk Road united the peoples of Europe and Asia, played a positive role in the development of

interstate economic relations, and served as a connecting link in international relations. Currently, internal and interstate transport, economic and passenger connections of the regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan are carried out by the state joint-stock company "Uzbekistan Railways".

A developed network of railways is related to the material and technical base of transport services, its economic connections, the quality of providing services to the needs of the national economy, the proportionality of the economic development of the country's regions and sectors to the level of cargo carrying capacity, and depends on a plane. The government of the republic attaches great importance to the creation of a single transport railway network that covers the country and its territories, which are busy with economic activities.

From the first years of independence, the improvement of the transport and communication system of Uzbekistan was required to solve the problems left over from the old authoritarian system. These problems consisted of ending the passage of the railways leading to the Surkhandarya region of our republic and the Republic of Karakalpakstan through the territory of neighboring Turkmenistan, the construction of highways in the republic that meet the demands of the new world, and the reconstruction of the existing ones, and the improvement of aviation infrastructure.

In order to solve the above-mentioned problems, the strategic directions of the reform of the transport system were defined and the work of creating a unified national transport system in the republic was started. The foundation was laid for

the development of all sectors of the industry - railway, automobile, air transport. Urgent tasks to increase the competitiveness of roads and railways in Uzbekistan were determined.

The national program for the period 1995-2010 of the role of the Republic of Uzbekistan in Central Asia, the development of industry and other sectors, and the rapid development and improvement of economic relations with neighboring countries was developed.

In order to continue creative work in the republic, the adoption of the program for the rapid development of the construction of transport and communication infrastructure in 2011-2015 is inextricably linked with the programs implemented for the prospective development of the production, transport and engineering-communication infrastructure network of the economy of the country and regions. allowed further development.

Strategic directions for the formation of an integrated railway network in our country have been determined. In this regard, in 1994-2001, the railway "Navoiy-Uchkuduk-Nukus" with a length of about 700 kilometers was completed. As a result, since the first years of the operation of this railway line, a large amount of various consumer goods have been delivered to the Republic of Karakalpakstan and Khorezm region.

In order to further improve the railway network in the republic, a new railway "Guzor-Boysun-Kumkurgan" was built.

On August 24, 2007, the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, in his speech at the ceremonial opening of the Tashguzar-Boysun-Kumkurgan railway, said: The fact that this 223-kilometer railway was put into operation in a short

period of time, in 33 months, two years ahead of schedule, is undoubtedly a huge event in the history of our country. I think we are telling the same truth," he said.

The most important significance and essence of these great works is that the Uzbek people once again demonstrated their strength and what they are capable of. This was done at an altitude of 1,800 meters above sea level, along the mountainous regions of hard rocks, under the scorching heat of summer and the harsh winds of winter, where railway tracks were laid, Tashguzar and Dehkhanaabad, Oqrabot and Darband, Boysun and Kumqo. It can also be seen in the example of the construction of 6 new stations and 9 stations with passenger platforms, such as Rgon.

In particular, the construction of social infrastructure facilities, such as production facilities, schools, medical facilities, water and gas networks, which ensure road safety at all stations, shows that this project was implemented at the level of the most modern requirements.

During the construction of the Tashguzar-Boysun-Kumkurgan railway, 43 bridges, including railway bridges and overpasses, were created. The fact that 9 of these bridges were built at a height of 1500 meters above sea level shows that unprecedented work has been done in this regard, which has not been seen before in the experience of Uzbekistan¹.

The construction and commissioning of this railway was of great importance in the development of the republic. This road made it possible to establish a single and integrated railway transport communication system throughout the country, a tool that connects the southern region of the republic - the oases of

Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya with other regions.

This road will allow Uzbekistan to access and export to foreign countries, first of all, through the Trans-Afghan railway corridor, directly to the ports of the Indian Ocean, South and Southeast Asian countries in the near future, at the same time, it dramatically increased the republic's capacity to expand its transit role.

As a result of the launch of the railway network, about 2.5 thousand additional new jobs will be created for the organization of freight and passenger traffic, railway maintenance and road safety. was created. In addition, more than 4,000 people got jobs in newly established enterprises and service outlets, especially in the spheres of small business and private entrepreneurship.

New opportunities have appeared for the development of natural underground resources of the region. The socio-economic life of Surkhandarya and Kashkadarya regions has undergone radical changes, and the living conditions of the population have increased. The distance of cargo and passenger transportation has decreased to 170 kilometers, and the travel time has decreased to 7 hours. As a result, the weight of transit and local cargo transported by railway has increased significantly. This is evidenced by the fact that 5 million tons of cargo were

transported by this railway last year, of which 4 million tons were transit cargo.

In 2013, under the leadership of the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, another huge project - the construction of the 125-kilometer "Angren-Pop" electrified railway was launched. It was completed in 2016. In the future, this railway will connect not only the regions of the Fergana Valley with other regions of the republic, but also Europe with China, and will further increase the transit potential of our country.

During the years of independence, great importance was attached to the electrification of railways. In the past period, the Khovos-Bekabad, Khovos-Jizzakh lines were electrified, and the electrification of the Marokand-Karshi route is scheduled to be completed ahead of schedule. High-speed electric trains have started running on the Tashkent-Samarkand-Bukhara route. As a result, it was possible to reduce the costs of using trains by 20% and increase the speed of passenger and cargo transportation by 1.3 times. "Afrosiyab" trains connecting the cities of Tashkent and Samarkand with high speed have been launched for the first time in the Central Asian region.

In short, during the years of independence, our country has become a huge construction site. New lines are being built in the railway sector, which is considered the "blood vessel" of the economy, and the quality of traffic is being strengthened.

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